

A Robust VBA Code for the Pie Chart Display of Turkish Music Usuls

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Abstract

The authors introduce a robust VBA code that can automatically run in the form of a *macro* under Microsoft Excel^(TM) to display Turkish Music usuls (rhythmic patterns) as pie charts. Musical notes are clockwise drawn using rotated ASCII characters from a music font (e.g., of the user's choosing) for each given beat. Relevant unbeamed note glyphs thus replace numerical values (e.g., fractions such as "1/2" representing a "half note") which ordinarily divide, and appear in the slices of, the pie charts, while the widths of the slices are preserved in accordance with given note durations. The code also enables users to specify font styles such as **bold**, *italic*, underlined as a novel means to indicate accentuation and which hand/mallet strikes the beat detail in the expression and elucidation of traditional beat syllables called "*düm-tek*" – that can just as well be substituted with the older, yet mostly outdated, "*ten-nen-ni*" syllables or similar traditional guidelines pertaining to diverse ethnic rhythms around the world. The downloadable Excel file which contains the VBA code is prepared in such a way as to include subsidiary embedded macros geared to help automate new worksheet creation for additional usuls aside from the currently provided presets, or similar beat patterns as the user may designate.

Keywords

Pie Chart Usul, Pie Chart Rhythm, Düm-tek, Visual Basic^(TM) for Applications (VBA), Microsoft Excel^(TM) Macro

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«Overview»

In the theoretical historiography of Middle Eastern music, the "Edvar" (*pl.* "Devir": Cycles) method for circumferentially describing and navigating usuls (i.e., oriental rhythmic patterns) — much the same as with oriental scales — had been utilized for centuries until the advent of Westernization. Before Eurogeneric staff notation was commonly adopted in the region by the mid-19th Century, the basic units making up these rhythmic patterns and musical scales alike were drawn as points on a circle the way exemplified in Fig.1 [Tura, 2001] and Fig.2 [Uygun, 1999]:

While bringing note durations (i.e., note values in Arabic numerals) and "*düm-tek*" (or "*ten-nen-ni*") syllables together into a wheel representation was thought of and implemented using Arabic script in music theory tractates since a long time

Figure 1. Kantemir’s “Kitabu ’İlmi’l-Musiki ’ala vechi’l-Hurufat”, p. 168: Zencir Usul.

Figure 2. Urmevi’s “Kitabu’l-Edvar” - (A) Nüshası 16a, p.79: Rast Dairesi.

as shown, and although there are clear educational merits to it even now, said approach was discontinued by the beginning of the 20th Century up to this day.

With the onset of computer technologies, it has become possible to not only visualize circumambulating rhythms and scales, but also to obtain accurate playback from any representation. To such an end, one may draw attention to, say, the nifty *SCALA* software programmed by de Coul [2019], as well as the freeware *Usul-Velvele Editor* application designed by the second co-author [Keçecioglu, 2010] — which, however, uses as yet a commonplace Eurogeneric percussion staff notation.

When digital playback is not a concern, but professional typesetting is, one may find it desirable to rekindle the historical Edvar idea with a straightforward computer code that allows the user to transcribe usul beats into the slices of a pie chart using Eurogeneric note glyphs (or any set of desired font characters), and which assures that the widths of the slices are automatically calibrated according to the duration of the beats (which apparently has not been done before), and where the which hand/mallet strikes at a given moment information is possible to indicate by accentuating the font style for the traditional *düm-tek* syllables or similar guidelines. (This last feature — relying simply on singular instances or combinations of **bold**, *italic*, underlined — is a novel implementation by the authors).

All of the above can be and has been achieved via a robust VBA code that runs in the form of a macro under Microsoft Excel^(TM) that is readily downloadable from the first author’s website [Yarman, 2016].

Some caveats concerning the proposed pie chart approach are as follows: i) In our graphic representations, we make no *a priori* assumption on the temporal evenness or mathematical precision of beats, nor do we exclude attempts toward exact articulation and chronological equalization; ii) we do not presume the absolute correctness of any usul with regards to its tempo, meter, beat onsets, beat accentuations or rhythmic embellishments as given in the literature, for which we have, in this study, referred solely to the conventional textbook by Özkan [2006]; iii) we understand that Excel macros are proprietary, but may nevertheless still be reliable for the mass-distribution of our code.

For comparison with adjacent ideas, a cursory survey of the literature making up the academical backbone of a significant part of the innovative software drumbeat market reveals the presence of some prominent ring-shaped representations of rhythms (most of which are available for scrutiny in the digital domain). Among them can notably be cited *Rhythm and Transforms* (particularly its Chapter 2: “Visualizing and Conceptualizing Rhythm”) by Sethares [2007], *The Geometry of Musical Rhythm: What Makes a “Good” Rhythm Good?* (particularly its Chapter 7 — p.45 — onward featuring circular diagrams) by Toussaint [2013], a precursor study to the latter by Liu and Toussaint [2010], and a master’s thesis by Snyder [2014] demonstrating the computer programming of a

”Circular Entrainment” that draws heavily from the theoretical framework of Toussaint (cf. also Demaine et al. [2005]) as well by London [2006]. These sources especially encapsulate the notion of nested rhythms and necklace patterns with beat-skipping, permutation and rotation operations.

Along this line, a particularly useful blog post by Hein [2014] — who is the author of the master’s thesis “*Designing the Drum Loop: A constructivist iOS rhythm tutorial system for beginners*” — summarizes a plethora of pertinent products built on said foundations. Another web article by CDM [2011] and yet another feature column by Synthtopia [2015] does similar coverage.

1. Reviving the circumsyllabic Edvar approach in the digital pie chart representation of Turkish music usuls

Turkish Art Music rhythmic patterns called “usuls” feature basic and compound meters up to 124 pulses per bar, with one or more filled-beat (“velveleli”) variants for each. With respect to their usul analogues in Turkish Art music, metric structure varieties that take place in the Folk music of Turkey too exhibit similar construction of rhythms from binary, tertiary and quaternary sub-groups of beats. Permutation of the beats in an irregularly divided segment (e.g. a tertiary or quaternary sub-group) often yields characteristically syncopated metric structures that are specifically named, such as the 9/8 “Aksak” (meaning “Limping”), the 9/8 “Evfer” (meaning “Profuse”), and the 9/8 “Raks Aksağı” (meaning “Limping of the Dance(r)”), etc... (cf. Baumann [2013].)

Internalizing the beat patterns of an usul requires familiarity with the classical “*düm-tek*” or the older (yet mostly outmoded) “*ten-nen-ni*” syllables that not only are associated with poetic meters, but also communicate the status of the beating/drumming hand; i.e. whether left, right or both hands are to be used in the sequence. For instance, Doğrusöz [2017] says:

“... A group of beats that forms a cycle and is divided into certain segments is called a rhythmic pattern (*usul*) by the theoreticians of music in the Islamic World. These rhythmic patterns are shown as circles just because they are repeated and carried through. Since music is not considered any different from poetry, rhythmic patterns are made of basic elements of poetic prosodic meter (*aruz*). The principal elements are; *ten, te-ne, te ne, te nen, ta ni, te ne nen, te ne ne nen* which is used in the teaching of both the prosodic meter and the usuls. ...”

However, “*düm-tek*” syllables by themselves do not reliably import note durations, and definitely do not contain accurate accentuation information. For that reason, the official theory called *Arel-Ezgi-Uzdilek* incorporates a special staff notation for percussion instruments based on just two

2. Velveleli Raks-Aksağı “mümkün”

$$2. \text{ Velveleli Raks-Aksağı} = (2+3+2+2) / 8$$

Figure 3. Pie chart display of the II. (“plausible”) Velveleli (Filled-beat) Raks Aksağı.

staff lines for the right and left hand respectively in order to transcribe usuls.

However, hand-written or printed scores seldom notate the usul part. Also, haphazard or perfunctory mensural subdivision of many compound usuls means that the natural arrangement of their beats is forfeited. Most of the time, even critical accentuation marks are neglected in scoring an usul. As a result of this, some neoteric theoretical exercises were attempted to re-explain usuls (cf. Sayan [2010]), yet none of them made a serious impact on traditional music education in Turkey.

Since usul learning is a praxis mostly depending on rote, it stands to reason that the historical roots, as seen in Edvar tractates, should not be severed. At the same time, any new teaching method must be easy to understand and non-challenging to execute if one expects it to gain a foothold. Hence, we present in this study a circumsyllabic pie chart method akin to old treatises on mode and usul cycles (i.e., “Edvars”), where note values are placed in the relevant slices of the pie chart in a clockwise rotated fashion using Euro-generic noteheads having unbeamed stems, each of which is paired up with textually accentuated “*düm-tek*” syllables.

The particulars of our pie chart exposition in Fig.3 below are as follows:

- 1) Beats are drawn in the clockwise direction,

- and our usul illustration begins at 12:00 o'clock.
- 2) “Düm-tek” syllables are matched with note duration glyphs in the auto-adjusted pie chart slices.
 - 3) **Bold** font style indicates the right hand, normal font style (“regular”) indicates the left hand, *italic* font style indicates both hands.
 - 4) Paired beats such as “Te-ke” and “Dü-me” are hyphenated. These can never be conceived as independent.
 - 5) If all letters are capitals (DÜM), the beat will have a *forte* dynamic; if only the first letter is a capital (Düm), the beat will have a *mezzoforte* dynamic; if every letter is uncapitalized (düm), the beat will have a *piano* dynamic; and if all letters are separated with a space character (d ü m), the beat will have a *pianissimo* dynamic.
 - 6) For (long) usuls which require a plethora of beats that cannot fit into a single circle, more than one cycle can be drawn (e.g., using different worksheets).
 - 7) Alternative beats can be indicated between parentheses just as shown in the picture.
 - 8) In some special cases, in order to indicate that both qudum (drum) mallets are to strike on the left qudum together, the beat is underlined.

The macro code, which will be detailed momentarily, transforms quantities pertaining to note values in the “A” column of the Excel worksheets into circumjacently distributed musical notes. It moreover formats the *düm-tek* syllables entered into the “B” column as font styles in the manner explained above (or as preferred by the user). If one wishes it, one may enter “*ten-nen-ni*” syllables according to the method explained herein, or as per different customized guidelines, into the “B” column.

In column “A”, number 1 signifies a quarter note (i.e., ♩), number 2 signifies a half note (i.e., ♪), and number 4 signifies a whole note (i.e., ♩). As per this logic, the 1/2 value indicates a one eighth note (i.e., ♩), the 1/4 value indicates a one sixteenth note (i.e., ♩), and the 1/8 value indicates a one thirty-second note (i.e., ♩).

The user is furthermore free to choose any other set of glyphs from the same or another desired font for the representation of note durations via symbols. In light of the application thus-far specified, one can hence variegate any usul by a doubling or halving of its note values simply upon the re-assignment of font glyphs, or upon the batch modification of the numerical values in the “A” column of the worksheets.

2. The USUL-EDVAR macro code

Fig.4 enumerates some of the essential integer and string command shorthands in the preamble of our usul pie chart macro code. For instance, H1 to H8 will be utilized as placeholders

```
Code Snippet
Option Explicit

Dim e As Integer
Dim VS As Integer
Dim A() As Integer
Dim T As Single
Dim H(1 To 8) As String
Dim N() As Integer
Dim V() As Single
Dim x As Integer

...

Dim St As Integer
Dim En As Integer
Dim Ek As Integer

...
```

Figure 4. Preamble to the macro code where essential integers and strings are defined.

for the character keycodes related to the abovementioned note duration glyphs (Chr\$(101), for example) from the font of our choosing. These are detailed in Fig.5, along with the specification of an OPUS TEXT font — which is publicly available via Sibelius Scorch™. If this font is missing, a subsidiary macro, as seen in Fig.6, will give an error message. The user may, of course, designate any other font for the purpose.

After the note values are inputted in Arabic numerals and/or fractions to the column “A” of an Excel worksheet, they have to be identified by the macro code and operated on for the existing range of textstrings. Fig.7 hints at the assignment of note glyphs from the selected font to anything that exists within A1:A36 in the worksheet. This part (i.e., “1 to 36”) can be modified to handle a greater or lesser range as the user may deem fit.

Fig.7 also indicates that the note glyphs from the chosen font will each be rotated (so as to lock on to the radial lines from the origin) as the code traverses the pie chart clockwise. With the code snippet shown in Fig.8, note values are assigned to font glyph placeholders H1 thru H8. Note that H7 and H8 are synthetically kerned glyphs by the macro itself, where a dotted note may be tied to an undotted note.

Once the necessary definitions have been made concerning the contents of column “A”, it is then time to focus on the font styles of the contents of column “B” in the worksheet. Fig.9 shows how our code assures that the **bold**, *italic*, underlined and even ~~strikethrough~~ or **colored** text in column “B” will be reflected as such to the pie chart. The results are demonstrated in the relevant outermost slices of the USUL-EDVAR pie chart in Fig.3.

Going back a little bit, the code snippet shown in Fig.10 calibrates the font sizes according to the size of the pie chart, which is nominally populated with the contents of columns A1:A36 and B1:B36. Needless to say, the user may customize the sizes as necessary.

Finally, among the embedded subsidiary macros that facilitate worksheet automation, the code snippet given in Fig.11

```
Code Snippet
'
' USUL-EDVAR Macro
' Copies rhythmic contents of A & B Columns to the Pie Chart,
' and replaces note duration numerals with (rotated) musical engravings
' from font.
'
' -This CODE is created by - (Yük. Müh.) M. Uğur Keçecioğlu (M. Sci.) -
' - tarafından bu KOD yazılmıştır.
'
'
Private Sub Worksheet_Activate()

If FontExists("Opus Text") Then          '*****
  FontName = "Opus Text"                '***** Modify to use personal
  ' music font.
Else
  MsgBox "Font file not found! - OPUS TEXT - Font dosyası bulunamadı!",
  vbExclamation '*****
  'Warning for when the required font is not installed. (Cf.
  ' CHECKFONT Macro.)
End If

If Not (Range("D5") = vbNullString) Then Exit Sub
  'Prevents running the code when cell "D5" contains any text.

H(1) = Chr$(119): H(2) = Chr$(104): H(3) = Chr$(113)
H(4) = Chr$(101): H(5) = Chr$(120): H(6) = Chr$(121)
H(7) = Chr$(113) & Chr$(46): H(8) = Chr$(104) & Chr$(46)
  'You may modify the ASCII codes above for when using your personal
  ' music font.
```

Figure 5. Beginning section of our macro: Utilization of the OPUS TEXT font.

```
Code Snippet
VS = 0: T = 0
For e = 1 To 36
  If Range("A" & e).Value > 0 Then
    ReDim Preserve V(e)
    V(e) = Range("A" & e).Value
    VS = VS + 1
    T = T + V(e)
  Else
    Exit For
  End If
Next e

ReDim A(1 To VS)
St = 0: En = 0
For e = 1 To VS
  St = St + En
  En = V(e) / T * 360
  Ek = St + (En / 2)
  Select Case Ek
    Case 0 To 89: A(e) = Ek * -1
    Case 90: A(e) = 0
    Case 91 To 180: A(e) = (Ek - 180) * -1
    Case 181 To 269: A(e) = 180 - Ek
    Case 270: A(e) = 0
    Case 271 To 360: A(e) = 360 - Ek
  End Select
Next e

...

Next e
Range("A36").Select
End Sub

...

Private Sub Worksheet_SelectionChange(ByVal Target As Range)

End Sub
```

Figure 7. Specifying and operating on the given range for column “A” in a worksheet.

```
Code Snippet
'
' CHECKFONT Macro
' -Checks whether the required font by USUL-EDVAR Macro is installed or
' - not.
'
' - Taken FROM [http://www.freevbcode.com/ShowCode.asp?ID=1245]
' - adresinden ALINMIŞTIR.
'
'
Function FontExists(FontName As String) As Boolean          '*****
  oFont.Name = FontName                                    '*****
  bAns = StrComp(FontName, oFont.Name, vbTextCompare) = 0 '*****
  FontExists = bAns                                       '*****
End Function
```

Figure 6. Embedded subsidiary macro for checking whether the music font is available.

```
Code Snippet
ReDim N(1 To VS)
For e = 1 To VS
  Select Case V(e)
    Case 4: N(e) = 1
    Case 2: N(e) = 2
    Case 1: N(e) = 3
    Case 1 / 2: N(e) = 4
    Case 1 / 4: N(e) = 5
    Case 1 / 8: N(e) = 6
    Case 1 + 1 / 2: N(e) = 7
    Case 2 + 1 / 2: N(e) = 8
  End Select
Next e

ActiveSheet.ChartObjects("Chart 1").Activate
'Chart reference can be different than specified.
ActiveChart.SeriesCollection(1).DataLabels.Select

With Selection
  .HorizontalAlignment = xlCenter
  .VerticalAlignment = xlCenter
End With
```

Figure 8. Describing in the macro code note values and assigning them to glyphs.

```
Code Snippet
For e = 1 To VS
ActiveChart.SeriesCollection(2).Points(e).DataLabel.Select
Selection.Characters.Text = Range("B" & e).Characters.Text
Selection.AutoScaleFont = False
Selection.Orientation = 0
Selection.Characters.Font.Name = Range("B" & e).Characters.Font.Name
Selection.Characters.Font.Size = Range("B" & e).Characters.Font.Size

For x = 1 To Len(Range("B" & e).Characters.Text)
If Not ((Range("B" & e).Characters(Start:=x, Length:=1).Text) =
Chr$(13)) Then
If Not ((Range("B" & e).Characters(Start:=x, Length:=1).Text) =
Chr$(10)) Then
Selection.Characters(Start:=x, Length:=1).Font.Bold = Range("B"
& e).Characters(Start:=x, Length:=1).Font.Bold
End If
End If
Next x

',
',
',
',
',
'Italic ...
'Underline ...
'Strikethrough...
'Color...

Next e
```

Figure 9. Applying font styles to “düm-tek” syllables in the column “B” of a worksheet.

```
Code Snippet
For e = 1 To VS
ActiveChart.SeriesCollection(1).Points(e).DataLabel.Select
Selection.Characters.Text = H(N(e))
Selection.AutoScaleFont = False
Selection.Orientation = A(e)
Selection.Characters(Start:=1, Length:=1).Font.Name = FontName
'#####
Select Case VS
Case 2 To 14: Selection.Characters(Start:=1, Length:=1).Font.Size
= 20
Case 15 To 18: Selection.Characters(Start:=1, Length:=1).Font.Size
= 18
Case 19 To 24: Selection.Characters(Start:=1, Length:=1).Font.Size
= 16
Case 25 To 36: Selection.Characters(Start:=1, Length:=1).Font.Size
= 14
Case Else: MsgBox "Font size undefined for number of
beats in the column! / Sütundaki darp sayısına dair font boyutu
tanımlanmamıştır!", vbExclamation
'Warning for when font size remains undefined for more than 36
rows of beats.
End Select

Selection.Characters(Start:=1, Length:=1).Font.ColorIndex = 1
Next e
```

Figure 10. Calibrating the font sizes according to the size of the pie chart.

```
Code Snippet
'
' GETDATA Macro
' Gets Data from Another Workbook
'
'→ Inspired FROM [http://www.mrexcel.com/forum/excel-questions/
156384-copy-paste-special-numerous-sheets.html] adresinden
ESINLENİLMİŞTİR.
'
Private Sub CommandButton3_Click()
→ FileName = Application.GetOpenFilename(FileFilter:="Excel workbook
(*.xls)*.xls", Title:"Open data")
'Source file: change as you will.
→ If FileName = "False" Then MsgBox "Cancelled by user. / Kullanıcı
tarafından iptal edildi." Else Application.Workbooks.Open (FileName)
ActiveWorkbook.ActiveSheet.Select
ActiveWorkbook.ActiveSheet.Range("A:B").COPY
Windows("Usuller-Ozkan.xls").Activate
'Destination file: change as you will.
Columns("A:B").Select
→ Selection.PasteSpecial Paste:=xlPasteAll, Operation:=xlNone,
SkipBlanks _
:=False, Transpose:=False
Range("A1").Select

End Sub
```

Figure 11. Getting data from another workbook’s columns A & B.

serves to import the contents of columns “A” & “B” from another Excel file into the currently open worksheet.

3. Conclusion

In this study, we proposed a method to display usuls pertaining to Turkish Art music (or any other set of rhythmic patterns belonging to another genre, for that matter) as double-layered pie charts of high typesetting quality containing both note durations and “düm-tek” syllables — that can just as well be replaced with the older “ten-nen-ni” syllables or similar rhythmic guidelines. For our purposes, we have referenced Özkan [2006] and tried to systematize his usul explanations under a Microsoft Excel^(TM) workbook beginning from Nim Sofyan (2/4) up until Velveleli Lenk Fahte (10/4) using a specially crafted macro code.

The MS Excel macro code scripted in the VBA language which serves to draw the graphics was developed by the second co-author according to demand and provided instructions by the first co-author. Making the code available online as such should help to distribute it worldwide, and is expected to yield various educational benefits in teaching percussion music when playing diverse rhythms.

Using the suggested method, we have hence revived the historical Edvar idea digitally and visually, and now claim that usuls (akin to how they were shown in historical treatises, but hereinafter supplemented with Eurogeneric note glyphs) can be learned and executed with comparative ease.

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